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Review Article

Plumbago Zeylanica: A Valuable Resource for Natural Health Products

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ABSTRACT

Chitrak, *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn., is well known as a medicinal herb with substantial health benefits. This is a perennial herb, which is a member of the Plumbaginaceae family. The plant has a long-term use in traditional Indian medicine as well as other regional medicine. Chitrak significance has increased because of its various pharmacological qualities. The plant can therapeutically act as an anti-inflammatory, anti-obesity, analgesic effects, anti-cancer, anti-fertility effects, and anti-blood coagulate. The plant parts and roots have been used since centuries in ayurvedic medicine to cure conditions like arthritis, leprosy, skin conditions, and digestive problems. The promising effects of this plant are attributed to an important bio-active compound called Plumbagin and phytochemicals such as Flavonoids, Alkaloids, and some key elements that the leaf possess. Despite its extensive medicinal benefits, caution is advised as overuse can lead to adverse effects. Even in today's era of Modern Medicine, many individuals rely on consumption of herbal medicine. To meet the current demand and to support the health of individuals, the review aims to seek the attention of future researchers to fully utilize the naturally available resources into a natural remedy such as herbal formulations like decoction, tea, or nutraceuticals for treating the different health ailments around the world.

INTRODUCTION

Our planet is endowed with a vast array of medicinal plants. Despite their inclusion into traditional treatments, those medicinal plants have been used for decades to treat ailments in humans. However, after the COVID-19 epidemic shook the world, people have gotten more concerned regarding their health and are looking for naturally

derived teas, decoctions, supplements, or extracts from medicinal plants. In fact, most of the medicinal herbs produce a wide variety of biologically active compounds that can be used to treat several diseases. These substances are useful in the development of new drugs because they often contain antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant qualities. The World Health

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Organization is promoting the use of herbal and Ayurvedic medicine in developing countries, based on a reported study [Error! Reference source not found..Error! Reference source not found..Error! Reference source not found.].

The popular medicinal plant *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn. Chitraka, Chitrak, Chitramulam, Swethachitram, leadwort, or doctor bush are a few names for *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn, which is a member of Plumbaginaceae family, popularly known as the Plumbago family. The generic name *Plumbago* comes from the Latin word *Plumbum*, which means "lead," and suggests that the plant might cure lead palsy or that its sap might result in lead-coloured stains on the skin. *Zeylanica* means "of Ceylon" [Error! Reference source not found.]. The Plumbaginaceae family comprises 280 species and 10 genera [Error! Reference source not found..Error! Reference source not found..Error! Reference source not found.]. *Plumbago capensis* L., *Plumbago zeylanica* L., and *Plumbago indica* L. (*Plumbago rosea* L.) are the three species that comprise the genus and are found throughout India [Error! Reference source not found.]. [Error! Reference source not found.]. Andhra Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, West Bengal, Chhattisgarh, Telangana, and Tamil Nadu are all plains districts where *Plumbago Zeylanica* can be found [3][5]. For herbal and pharmaceutical medicine, the components of the plant Chitrak are Qualified [6].

PHYLOGENETIC CLASSIFICATION OF *Plumbago zeylanica*:

The plant belongs to the kingdom Plantae and falls under the order Caryophyllales. It is part of the family Plumbaginaceae and the genus *Plumbago*. The species is identified as *Zeylanica* [1] [3] [7].

DIVERSE NAMES FOR *Plumbago zeylanica* ACROSS REGIONS AND LANGUAGES

Different languages and geographical areas have different names for the plant *Plumbago zeylanica*. It is commonly referred to as Chitramulam and Tella Chitramulam in Telugu. It has various names like Chitra, Agni, Vahni, and Dahana in Sanskrit.

Leadwort, Ceylon leadwort, or doctor bush are common English and Chira, Chitraka, and Sheetraj in Hindi. It is known as Kodiveli and Chitramoolam in Tamil, and Chitramula, Vahini, and Bilichitra in Kannada. In Gujarati, it is known as Chitramula, whereas in Bengali, it is simply called Chitra. It is called Vellakeduveli in Malayalam and Chitra in Punjabi. It is known by the Marathi name Chitraka, the Kashmiri names Shatranja and Chitra, and the Oriya names Chitrapu and Ogni. Finally, it's called Ki Encok in Indonesian [1].

BOTANICAL DESCRIPTION:

Plumbago Zeylanica is a shrub or perennial dicot plant that grows in shaded areas and is evergreen and rambling [4].

Leaves: Leaves are simple, oval shaped with hairy margins and pointed end with surface smooth and shiny. The leaves measure 3-5 cm in width and 4-10 cm in length. They contain plumbagin, chitanone, plumbagic acid [1] [3,4].

Flower: White in coloured flowers that are odourless arranged regularly, bisexual, in long spike-like racemes inflorescence with length 10-25 cm. The calyx is arranged inferiorly, which are free tubular, spindle shaped, 5-10 ribbed. September to November is the growing period for Flowers [1] [4].

Fruit: Fruits are oblong, capsulated. Unripe fruits look green in colour with sticky hairs over it on ripening the fruits turn dark brown in colour. Fruits occurs from January to February. And the fruit has only one seed with 7.5-8mm in length [1] [4].

Roots: Roots are seldom branched with small warty projections. They vary ¼ to 2 inches or more than 2 inches in diameter. The root bark looks blackish-red in colour and reddish-brown when dried. It tastes bitter [1] [4].

Figure 1: Fresh Plumbago Zeylanica Leaves.

BIOACTIVE COMPOUND:

Plumbagin: The yellow-colored crystalline active component plumbagin (2-methyl-5-hydroxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone) is found in the plant parts of *Plumbago zeylanica*[8,9]. Several techniques, such as reverse-phase liquid chromatography, normal-phase chromatography, silica gel column chromatography, and Soxhlet apparatus, were used to isolate plumbagin from the roots[2]. Various biological activities, including antiviral, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, anticancer, and anti-diabetic properties, have been observed. Plumbagin may also be useful in treating a variety of conditions, such as diarrhea, hepatic toxicity, reproductive toxicity, skin issues, and elevated levels of white blood cells, serum phosphate, and acid phosphate. It has also been recognized that the structure of vitamin K and plumbagin seems to be similar[2] [7,9].

PHYTOCHEMICAL COMPOSITION:

To finding out if the plant parts contain phytoconstituents, numerous investigations have been performed. Using atomic emission spectrometry with inductive coupling of plasma (ICP-AES), researchers have successfully identified various minerals and trace elements present in the samples. Phytochemical screening of different PZ parts had shown that elements like

four macro-elements (Na, K, Ca, and Mg), are present in higher concentrations in the leaves, stems, and roots. Eight additional elements (Mo, Sb, Bi, Cd, Sr, Pb, Cd, and As) and five vital microelements (Zn, Fe, Mn, Cr, and Co) are contained. These elements are generally present in many antioxidant and anticancer medications. By employing column chromatography, it was discovered that the aerial parts included indole-3 carboxaldehyde, plumbagin, isoshinanolone, plumbagic acid, beta-sitosterol, 4 hydroxybenzaldehyde, trans-cinnamic acid, vanillic acid, and 2, 5-dimethyl-7 hydroxy chromone[2,3] [7].

CHEMICAL COMPOUNDS IN LEAVES:

An investigation was carried out to see if any chemical components were detected in the PZ leaf chloroform extracts. Two varieties of *P. zeylanica* leaves were used; one was grown in Palembang, South Sumatra (PZSS), and the leaves were harvested, cleaned, and allowed to air dry for eighteen days away from direct sunlight. A blender was then used to powder the dried leaves. *P. zeylanica* leaf powder, which was acquired from the Herbadream Store in Surakarta, Central Java (PZCJ), was another. Later, 80g of PZCJ leaf powder was dissolved in 800ml of chloroform, while 6.5g of crushed PZSS was macerated in 65ml of chloroform for five days. Using a rotatory evaporator set to 60 degrees Celsius and 52 rpm for 20 minutes, the extracts were filtered and dried out. For additional analysis, gas chromatography-mass spectrometry analysis was employed. Both the PZSS and PZCJ chloroform extracts consisted the ten highest peaks in the chromatogram. Among the secondary metabolites of PZSS and PZCJ that are highly advantageous to human health are phytol and beta-sitosterol. Both extracts often contain compounds such as 1 undecanol, dodecyl acrylate, tributyl acetyl citrate, and decyl propanoate. Compared to PZCJ, the percentage of these compounds in PZSS was lower. In the PZSS chloroform extracts, the highest percentage of

chemical compounds identified was 1-undecanol, while the highest percentage of dodecylacrylate was observed in PZCJ. Furthermore, the PZCJ chloroform extract included a trace quantity of plumbagin[10].

THERAPEUTIC BENEFITS:

Anti-inflammatory Activity: Several studies have investigated the anti-inflammatory activities of *Plumbago zeylanica* L. extracts. Extracts of leaves in acetone and petroleum ether at dosage levels of 200 and 400 mg/kg dramatically decreased carrageenan-induced inflammation in rats. This was probably because they decreased prostaglandin synthesis. At a dosage of 250 mg/kg, a hydroalcoholic root bark extract demonstrated moderate anti-inflammatory effects in acute and in chronic inflammation models, like that of normal indomethacin, was determined. The researchers investigated the anti-inflammatory properties of shoot and root extracts at 25, 50, 75, and 100 mg/mL. Dichloromethane extract, at 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg, was shown to have effects like those of diclofenac in effectively inhibiting carrageenan-induced paw oedema. In rats with adjuvant-induced arthritis, that a 250 mg/kg dose of a freeze-dried ethyl acetate fraction (PZE-6) successfully reduced paw volume, symptomatic result, and delayed-type hypersensitivity reaction, consequently managing joint inflammation. By decreasing the expression of high mobility group box 1 and consequent nuclear factor κ B (NF- κ B), tumor necrosis factor- α (TNF- α), and myeloperoxidase (MPO) activity, plumbagin was found to decrease inflammatory cascades[7].

Additionally, 30 patients in a clinical investigation in Jaipur who received a dosage of 4 mg of chitraka churna twice a day for 15 days demonstrated notable improvements in their inflammatory symptoms. These results highlight the potential of extracts from *Plumbago zeylanica* L. to treat inflammation using a variety of strategies [3].

Antioxidant Activity: The antioxidant activity of the *P. zeylanica* leaf extracts were assessed in the Ferric reducing antioxidant power assay (FRAP) study employing ascorbic acid as a point of reference. The findings showed that at greater doses, each extract had the greatest lowering ability. When compared to petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extracts, the methanol extract showed the greatest mgAAE/100 g dry weight, suggesting that it had a higher reducing power than the other extracts. At similar concentrations, the ethyl acetate extract had a higher reducing power than the petroleum ether extract, and the methanol extract had a higher reducing power than the ethyl acetate extract. According to these results, which were corroborated by earlier research, extracts from more polar solvents shown superior antioxidant activity in comparison to those from less polar solvents [11]. Taking ascorbic acid as a standard, the DPPH-free radical scavenging ability of *P. zeylanica* leaf extracts was verified by colour change and absorbance at different doses. Although they were all less effective than ascorbic acid, methanol extract had the highest scavenging activity, followed by petroleum ether and ethyl acetate extracts. The methanol extract demonstrated greater protective activity with a lower IC₅₀ value [11].

Antibacterial Activity: Using Muller Hinton agar media, the antibacterial activity of *P. zeylanica* leaf extracts was tested on four bacteria; methanol and ethyl acetate extracts showed significant activity, while petroleum ether extract was less effective; methanol extract inhibited *S. aureus*, *S. pyogenes*, *E. coli*, and *K. pneumoniae* with zones of inhibition 19 ± 0.4 , 20 ± 0.26 , 21 ± 0.16 , and 16 ± 0.43 mm, respectively; ethyl acetate extract showed the highest inhibition against *S. pyogenes* and *E. coli* with 22 ± 0.18 and 21 ± 0.14 mm, respectively; IC₅₀ values were 292 mg/L (methanol, *E. coli*), 294 mg/L (ethyl acetate, *S. pyogenes*), and 747 mg/L (petroleum ether) [11].

Analgesic Effects: The study investigated how rat's arthritis was affected by Complete Freund's Adjuvant (CFA). Different amounts of *Plumbago*

zeylanica (PZ) extract (150, 250, or 350 mg/kg) were injected into 96 rats. The analgesic effects of PZ were evaluated using the hot plate test. The rats given injections of 250 and 350 mg/kg of PZ had a longer reaction time than the control group, based upon the data. This implies that PZ possesses analgesic qualities. However, the impact peaked between 1 and 2 hours after injection and then began to diminish around 4 hours. The study's findings demonstrated that PZ could lessen arthritis-related discomfort in rats. PZ may be a viable new treatment for arthritis pain, according to the researchers[12].

Anticancer: Plumbagin, a naphthoquinone derived from the *Plumbago zeylanica* roots, has been revealed to have antibacterial and anticancer properties. Plumbagin used the mitochondrial route to cause apoptosis in human promyelocytic leukaemia cells. The tumor volume decreased by 64.49% in mice given intraperitoneal injections of plumbagin (2 mg/kg daily for three weeks), indicating that it could potentially use as an option for therapy for myeloid leukaemia[4].

Memory Enhancing Activity: The study examined how plumbagin affected the memory and learning of young male Swiss albino mice. For 15 days, mice were given physostigmine (0.1 mg/kg, I.P.) and plumbagin (4, 8, 16 mg/kg, p.o.). The Morris water maze was used for tracking behavioural parameters. Plumbagin decreased brain acetylcholinesterase activity, corrected amnesia caused by scopolamine and diazepam, and markedly improved learning and memory. According to the study's findings, plumbagin may help treat cognitive problems by considerably enhancing memory[1] [4].

Antifertility Activity: The antifertility properties of *Plumbago zeylanica* L. leaf extracts were evaluated. It came to know that the most effective doses of acetone and ethanol extracts to disrupt the estrous cycle in rats were 200 and 400 mg/kg, with the anti-ovulatory action reversing when the extracts were stopped. This implies that these extracts may have antifertility effects. Similarly, in

female Wistar rats with immature ovariectomies, assessed the anti-implantation activity of hydroalcoholic extracts and observed substantial effects at 200 mg/kg. The uterus changed structurally and functionally because of the extract's antiestrogenic properties. Possible antifertility effects of *Plumbago zeylanica* L. extracts is highlighted in both investigations[7].

Anti-Blood Coagulation Activity: The anticoagulation effects of *P. zeylanica* root extract was examined in eight groups of six Wistar rats. *P. zeylanica* and plumbagin ethanolic extracts were given to groups III and IV, respectively. On days 1, 15, and 31, platelet counts, prothrombin time (PT), clotting time (CT), and bleeding time (BT) were assessed. The results revealed no changes in platelet synthesis when compared to controls, but continued use was associated with a considerable drop in platelet adhesion and an increase in bleeding duration, which were explained by changes in platelet coagulation and adhesiveness. These results imply that the root extract of *P. zeylanica* has a major effect on coagulation and platelet function[4].

Wound Healing Activity: Using Wistar albino rats, it is investigated that methanolic extract of *P. zeylanica* roots' capacity to promote wound healing. They found that its ability to cure wounds is aided by the presence of phytochemicals such terpenoids, alkaloids, flavonoids, and saponins. It was discovered that these substances balanced oxidative stress and sped up the healing of wounds. The study demonstrated the chitrak plant's vast potential for wound treatment and its capacity to promote the healing process. These findings provide evidence to *P. zeylanica*'s traditional usage and root extract in herbal medicine indicating that an effective natural treatment for wound management[4].

An effect on the Central Nervous System: The hydroalcoholic extract of chitrak plant's leaf demonstrated strong central nervous system depressive action in combination with muscle relaxant qualities[1].

Anti-Obesity Activity: A clinical investigation to investigate *Plumbago zeylanica* L.'s anti-obesity properties on obese patients at I.P.G.T & R. Hospital in Jamnagar, Gujarat. For 45 days, the therapy included a low-calorie diet, 500 mg of *Plumbago zeylanica* L., and 1 g of haridra powder taken as capsules four times a day. The findings indicated that the plant extracts may have anti-obesity properties because the combination of *Plumbago zeylanica* L. and haridra powder significantly decreased patient weight when compared to haridra alone[7].

Figure 2: Therapeutic Benefits of *Plumbago zeylanica* L

AYURVEDIC USES:

Plumbago, also known as Chitrak in Ayurveda, is a versatile herb with numerous medicinal properties. In Ayurveda, *plumbago*, also known as chitrak, is a multipurpose herb with a variety of therapeutic uses. Its root powder promotes appetite and digestion, cures piles, and heals diarrhea. Plumbagin treats recurring colds and coughs by increasing immunity and aiding in the removal of nasal mucus. By lowering inflammation, the plant helps those with rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, chronic sinusitis, and bronchitis. Additionally, it improves liver function, reduces cholesterol, and stops the growth of prostate cancer cells. *Plumbago* is used externally to treat filariasis, skin irritation, and other skin conditions. According to Ayurveda, Chitrak is a rasayana that promotes general health and well-being by

revitalizing the body and balancing the vata and kapha doshas [1].

DOSAGE:

Commonly mentioned dosages are 1 to 1½ grams, 1.5 to 3 grams, 3½ to 7 grams, 4½ grams, and 3 to 5 grams[4]. Additionally, PL has been demonstrated to be nontoxic and to have both therapeutic and chemo preventive effects at doses of 200 ppm in the diet or 2 mg/kg of body weight administered intraperitoneally[1] [13].

TOXICITY:

Despite its medicinal benefits, over usage of *Plumbago zeylanica* can lead the way to toxic effects namely irritation, burning sensations in the tongue, throat, and stomach, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea, and weak pulse. It can also irritate pelvic organs in pregnant women, leading to abortion[1] [13].

CONCLUSION:

This is a review paper on *Plumbago zeylanica* Linn. It is commonly known as Chitramulam and is a well-recognised medicinal plant. It is a member of the Plumbaginaceae family and is widely used in Ayurvedic, Unani, and Indian traditional medicine. The entire plant is used all over the world because of its therapeutic properties. This plant is an abundant source of various bioactive compounds likely plumbagin, alkaloids, flavonoids, etc. It has been used to treat a wide range of diseases. This plant is also known to have antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anti-cancer properties. This plant has been traditionally taken advantage of treating a variety of ailments including leprosy, skin diseases, wound healing, indigestion, constipation, diarrhea, fever, etc. In recent years, there has been an enhanced attention in the use of herbal medicines for the treatment of various diseases. This has led to an increase in the demand for medicinal plants. Thus, the objective of this

review is to explore information related its pharmacological parameters and therapeutic applications so that future researchers could potentially use this plant in a nutraceutical and can make new formulations using this herb.

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